

Interaction with Industry

ESIWACE2 improves access to computing applications and expertise that enables industry to be more productive, leading to scientific excellence and economic and social benefit.

Goal: Improved competitiveness for European companies and small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) through access to CoE expertise and services

By giving industry the opportunity to build technology prototypes that are suited for the weather and climate community and verticals, the time-to-market for upcoming products will be positively affected – not only for this community, but also for other related verticals in data-intensive computing.

Widening the access to codes and fostering transfer of know-how to user communities, including specific and targeted measures for industry and SMEs

Through:

- Enhanced sharing of code, best practices and corresponding expertise through ESIWACE2 community services,
- Knowledge transfer on evolving new technologies (exascale hardware, heterogeneous computing, machine learning, containerisation) via workshops and white papers,
- Sharing improved tools, such as OASIS and XIOS, by the entire community,
- Fostering exchange of know-how on data management requirements between the weather and climate community and storage vendors (SEAGATE, DDN),
- Selected measures for industry provided through key performance indicators,

ESIWACE2 addresses the following industrial sectors: HPC vendors (software and hardware), storage industry.

Interested?

Get in touch with us:

Project Office: esiwace@dkrz.de

Register for our quarterly newsletter: <https://lists.dkrz.de/mailman/listinfo/esiwace-external>

Follow us on Twitter:
<https://twitter.com/esiwace/>

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Access our Results

OPEN ACCESS! We support Open Access!

All our results – publications and reports – are available on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace/>

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe Phase 2

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EC Contribution: 8.035 million €

Duration: 1 January 2019 – 31 December 2022

Consortium: 19 partners

Project Coordinator: German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ), Germany

esiwace
CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE IN SIMULATION OF WEATHER
AND CLIMATE IN EUROPE

Project Objectives

The path towards exascale computing holds enormous challenges for the community of weather and climate modelling regarding portability, scalability and data management that can hardly be faced by individual institutes. ESIWACE2 links, organises and enhances Europe's excellence in weather and climate modelling to:

- Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021 and
- Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.

To achieve these goals, ESIWACE2:

- Improves throughput and scalability of leading European weather and climate models and demonstrates the technical and scientific performance of the models in unprecedented resolution on pre-exascale EuroHPC systems,
- Evaluates and establishes new technologies such as domain specific languages and machine learning for use in weather and climate modelling,
- Enhances HPC capacity via services to the weather and climate modelling community to optimize code performance and allow model porting,
- Improves the data management tool chain for weather and climate simulations at scale,
- Fosters co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres, and
- Strengthens interactions of the community with the European HPC eco-system.

ESiWACE2 delivers configurations of leading models that can make efficient use of the largest supercomputers in Europe and run at unprecedented resolution for high quality weather and climate predictions. This is a beacon for the community in Europe and around the world.

Cloud water (kg/m²; white) and cloud ice (kg/m²; light blue) simulated with the ICON atmosphere model at a global resolution of 2,5 km.

Codes of Interest

Leading European weather & climate models (coupled models of atmosphere and ocean):

- ICON (German weather service and MPI-M),
- IFS (ECMWF and EC-Earth consortium),
- NEMO (European community ocean model),
- Dynamico (next generation French model by IPSL).

Support to other models, e.g. UM from UK Met Office

Services

ESiWACE2 plans to establish, evaluate and watch new technologies to prepare climate and weather simulations for the exascale era.

Direct services: Create a prototype for open services to the Earth system modelling community in Europe. The goal of the services is to foster col-

laborations that provide guidance, engineering, and advice to support exascale preparations for weather and climate models. All groups developing and maintaining weather and climate codes – not only the ESiWACE2 partners – can apply. Proposals for such collaboration projects will be peer-reviewed and when found eligible will be granted in-kind support by one of the partners involved.

Indirect services: Establish DSLs in the community, evaluate concurrent components to improve performance, evaluate containers to port Earth system models to new hardware and watch emerging technologies.

Trainings

ESiWACE2 serves the weather and climate community and the European HPC ecosystem.

ESiWACE2 co-designs and provides targeted education and training for one of the most challenging applications to shape the future of HPC in Europe.

Trainings are planned in ESiWACE2 on:

- I/O and HPC awareness,
- DSL,
- C++ for HPC,
- OASIS3-MCT,
- High performance Data Analytics,
- Docker,
- Summer school in HPC for weather and climate modelling.

Check the contents and calendar of the trainings:

www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings